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Effect Of YouTube Instructional Strategy on Academic Performance and Retention in Physics Among Secondary School Student in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined Effect of YouTube Instructional Strategy on Academic Performance and Retention in Physics Among Secondary School Student in Rivers State. Two (2) objectives guided the study, two (2) research questions were answered and two (2) hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 significance level. Quasi-experimental study was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprises of four thousand five hundred and seventy-one (4,571) senior secondary school 1 student (SSS1) in all 154 private secondary schools in Obio-Akpor LGA in Rivers State. A sample size comprising of fifty-one (51) senior secondary school 1 (SSS1) students drawn from intact classes in two selected private secondary schools in Obio-Akpor Local Government. The purposive sampling procedure was adopted to select the sample of the study. A validated multiple-choice Physics Performance Test (PPT) and Physics Retention Test (PRT) questions with a reliability co-efficient of 0.74 and 0.65 respectively were used for data collection. The data collected was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 25 employing both descriptive and inferential statistics of Mean, Standard Deviation and ANCOVA. The study found that YouTube instructional tool had a strong effect in enhancing students' academic performance and retention in Physics in Rivers State. There was also a significant effect of YouTube instructional tool in enhancing students' academic performance and retention. It was concluded that YouTube instructional strategy enhances academic performance and retention in physics among secondary school student in Rivers State. Finally, the study recommended among others that educational policymakers should incorporate YouTube-based learning resources into the Physics curriculum to boost students' academic performance since it had a significant effect on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Keywords: YouTube Instructional Strategy, Physics, academic performance

INTRODUCTION

The entire basis of social and economic progress in education is the secret to success and the only path for long-term, steady economic growth. The most effective way to lower poverty, inequality, crime, and violence is through education. By giving people access to better employment, greater earnings, positive behavioral patterns, and an enhanced quality of life, it helps to lessen poverty and inequality. By equipping individuals with the finest information and skills necessary to engage in the global economy and make informed decisions, education lowers crime and violence. The growth of science and technology, which benefits mankind as a whole, depends on education. Globally, science and technology

are vital to the development of nations. Thus, scientific education and scientific education become essential if developing nations are to compete with developed ones. In addition to helping people reach their full potential, science education is a crucial instrument for society's technological advancement.

New innovations in classroom teaching and learning have been made possible by the revolution in technology (Falode, Sobowale, Saliu, Usman & Falode, 2016). The use of technology in the classroom has changed how educators organize their lessons, create lesson plans, and evaluate their students. Similar to how communication systems, learning materials, lesson plans, professional development, and learning productivity have altered due to developments in educational technology, these changes have also facilitated creativity and learning productivity (Garrett-White & Abel, 2017; Falode, et al. 2016; Mohammed, 2017). Furthermore, Maya (2024) found that students are getting more adept and quicker with new developments as a result of their increased use of contemporary technology. The focus of educators, practitioners, and academics has shifted towards the potential impacts of electronic tools on students' academic and behavioral performance, as a result of the recent attention that educational technology has garnered (Garrett-White & Abel, 2017).

Technology advancement and importance have altered many aspects of life, including education. Digital learning platforms are one such example of how this is happening. Because of the COVID-19 epidemic, which has compelled educational institutions to swiftly switch from in-person to online instruction in order to maintain the sustainability of education, digital learning platforms have grown in significance (Songkram & Osuwan, 2022). Numerous encounters with the format, organization, and content of traditional education have been made easier by digital learning platforms. When utilized for practice and study, digital learning platforms offer many forms of information regarding students' learning (Lima, Bastos & Varvakis, 2020).

Ogunode Johnson and Olatunde-Aiyedum (2022) claimed that because scientific curricula play a major role in the nation's technological advancement, they receive the utmost emphasis in Nigerian schools. Any country's technological advancement is hampered greatly if scientific education is not given top priority. Science education is an essential part of education that has the power to change people and society as a whole (Abubakar, 2024). Science education, according to Abubakar and Olamoyegun (2023), is a vital part of a country's growth and development and acts as a catalyst for breakthroughs in a variety of sectors. Because Science Education is crucial to a country's growth, it must be prioritized at all educational levels in every country.

Since science serves as the foundation for all current technical concepts, it has been said to be the cornerstone of contemporary technological advancement (Babagana, Yaki & Abubakar, 2021). It is a structured body of knowledge that is self-directed toward meeting needs and resolving issues for people. One of the largest and most important areas of human activity today is science. Today, science as a whole shape our understanding of the cosmos, planet, ourselves, and other living things. Various areas of science study nearly anything that can be viewed or detected. Science is now an essential component of human civilization. Nations that fail to acknowledge this important fact run the danger of jeopardizing the hopes and dreams of their next generation. It is important to remember that a country's ability to thrive is largely dependent on how well-educated its population is in science.

Statement of the Problem

Physics is a foundational science subject that supports the development of critical thinking, problem-solving, and technological advancement. In secondary schools across Rivers State, Physics remains a compulsory subject for students in the science track. However, internal classroom assessments and continuous evaluation records consistently reveal that many students perform poorly in the subject. The students struggle to grasp core Physics concepts, resulting in low comprehension, poor academic performance, and weak retention. These challenges persist despite the strategic importance of the subject in the national curriculum. This academic underachievement is especially troubling because Physics plays a vital role in preparing students for careers in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM). One of the main contributors to this poor performance is the continued reliance on traditional teaching methods. These approaches often characterized by lecture-based delivery, chalk-and-talk techniques, and minimal use of instructional media have limited capacity to explain abstract and complex

Physics concepts in a way that resonates with learners. As a result, students struggle not only to understand but also to retain what they have been taught, leading to weak foundational knowledge and poor academic outcomes. Therefore, study investigated effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance and retention in physics among secondary school student in Rivers State

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine the effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance and retention in Physics among Secondary School Student in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. examine the effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. determine the effect of YouTube instructional strategy on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised and answered in this study

1. What is the effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State?
2. What is the effect of YouTube instructional strategy on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant effect of YouTube instructional strategy on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Concept of Academic Performance

The main component and one of the main objectives of education is students' academic performance, which is defined as the knowledge they have acquired and is evaluated by teachers through grades or by educational goals that they have set for themselves and their teachers to accomplish over a predetermined amount of time (Narad and Abdullah, 2016). Academic institutions' primary goal is to help students achieve academic excellence by helping them demonstrate improved academic performance. Furthermore, for anyone who is concerned about education, academic performance is a very important factor. Since academic performance is, in fact, the center around which many important elements of the educational system revolve, researchers, parents, policy makers, and planners have all shown an interest in student academic performance (Kumar, Agarwal & Agarwal, 2021). Academic performance as an expression used to present students' scholastic standing and which is a function of various factors such as method of teaching, teachers' qualifications, students' home background, school environment, attitude, interest, among others (Zalmon, 2021; Nwile & Onojakaromah, 2022).

The impact of students' academic performance is multifaceted, despite the fact that it may seem like a straightforward result of education. Narad and Abdullah (2016) noted in their research that, at the most fundamental level, the success or failure of any academic institution depends largely upon the students' academic performance; they also reaffirmed the widely held belief that good academic performance indicates better career prospects and, consequently, a secure future. Students' academic performance is extremely significant because it affects both the social and economic development of any nation. The likelihood of producing skilled manpower that would support the country's social and economic growth increases with students' academic performance (Ali in Kumar, Argawal Argawal, 2021).

Concept of Academic Retention

One of the main objectives of education is to enable students to apply the knowledge and abilities they have acquired in earlier courses, in addition to performing certain tasks and recalling facts. Students should ideally be given the freedom to apply their knowledge and abilities in new circumstances. This important educational objective encourages lifelong learning and academic success (Bransford &

Schwartz in Puente & Kroesen, 2020). All educational systems aim to improve students' retention of the material they have learned. Consequently, the conventional wisdom that says retention is primarily determined by the material being taught disagrees with recent research that suggests educational elements like active learning strategies can also help students retain information (Puente & Kroesen, 2020).

The process of remembering a knowledge or idea after some time has passed is called retention. Learning could only be deemed to have occurred if such recall could be demonstrated. When a learner is able to remember and apply the knowledge they have previously been given, it is considered that they have learned meaningfully. It is important to remember that knowledge transfer to different domains of endeavor is impossible without retention (Ayoola, 2023). Musa, Achor, and Ellah (2021) describe retention as a mental preservation component. The senses provide the intellect with the raw elements for knowledge. Every time a stimulating scenario arises, the learned information in the mind must be kept as images; these retained images are brought back to life or replicated to facilitate memorization. There is a rising recognition that students' incapacity to make connections between what they have learned in the past and what they are studying now, as stated by Nwachukwu as referenced in Idiong *et al.* (2019), may be the cause of their poor science idea learning and retention.

According to the aforementioned claim, retention is the process of remembering or the capacity to bring back or identify knowledge or experiences. Since retention is evaluated in conjunction with accomplishment, it is likely that greater achievement will result from learning retention (Makinde & Yusef, 2018). Additionally, retention is the capacity to store information and recall it with ease. This suggests that information recall may be tainted and, as a result, lead to subpar performance if learners do not have appropriate storage structures created.

METHODOLOGY

The research adopted the quasi-experimental pre-test and post-test design. The design also includes a pre-test and a post-test, in which the purpose is to allow the researchers to determine the immediate effects of the treatment on the outcome variables. The population of the study consisted of all the four thousand, five hundred and seventy-one (4,571) senior secondary school students in one hundred and fifty-four (154) private secondary schools in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area. The sample for the study was fifty-one (51) secondary school student drawn from intact classes in the two selected private secondary schools in Obio-Akpor LGA. The two purposively selected secondary schools were chosen based on the following criteria The school must be government approved (a) It must have access to essential ICT tools such as computers, projectors, and internet connectivity (b) It must offer Physics as a subject at the Senior Secondary level (c) The schools must express willingness to participate in the study and allow their students to be exposed to experimental instructional strategy. (d) The schools must have a relatively stable electricity supply or alternative power sources to facilitate uninterrupted use of digital tools. The sample for the study was drawn using multi-stage sampling procedure. Two instruments for data collection were used for this study. These were a multiple-choice question. The first instrument was named Physics Performance Test (PPT) and the second Physics Retention Test (PRT) which was a reshuffled PPT. The PPT/PRT consist of twenty-five (25) items and it measured students' academic performance in Physics before and after the intervention while the PRT assessed students' retention of information learnt through YouTube. In order to ensure face and content validity, the instrument was presented some experts, two research experts in the field of Measurement and evaluation, university of Port Harcourt. The reliability of the instrument was determined using test-retest method. To achieve this, 20 copies of the PPT and the PRT were administered on 20 secondary school students selected from a private secondary school outside the study area. After an interval of two weeks, the instrument was reshuffled and re-administered to the same group. The initial and re-test scores of the subjects were correlated using Pearson Product Moment correlation and a reliability coefficient value of 0.74 was obtained for the PPT and 0.65 was obtained for the PRT. The instrument (PPT) was administered to the respondents by the researcher and two research assistants. Data collected was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level.

RESULTS

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: *What is the effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation on effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State

Group	N	Pre-test		Post test		Gain score
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Control	25	7.56	1.294	10.88	1.590	3.32
Experimental (YouTube)	26	7.42	2.176	17.46	1.985	10.04

Table 1 showed the mean and standard deviation analysis on effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State. The results indicate a difference in the academic performance of students in Physics between the Control Group and the Experimental Group (YouTube). The Control Group, consisting of 25 students, had a pre-test mean score of 7.56 with a standard deviation of 1.294, while their post-test mean score increased to 10.88 with a standard deviation of 1.590. This resulted in a gain score of 3.32, suggesting some improvement in performance after instruction. However, the relatively small gain score indicates that the traditional teaching method used for this group had a limited impact on students' academic progress. In contrast, the Experimental Group (YouTube), also comprising 26 students, started with a slightly lower pre-test mean of 7.42, but their post-test mean increased significantly to 17.46, with a standard deviation of 1.985. This resulted in a gain score of 10.02, which is almost three times higher than that of the control group. The larger gain score suggests that the YouTube instructional tool had a stronger effect in enhancing students' understanding and performance in Physics.

Research Question Two: *What is the effect of YouTube instructional strategy on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 2 Mean and standard deviation on effect of YouTube instructional strategy on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State

Group	N	Post test		Retention test		Gain score
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Control	25	10.88	1.590	11.08	1.498	0.2
Experimental (YouTube)	26	17.46	1.985	17.65	3.393	0.2

Table 2 showed the mean and standard deviation on effect of YouTube instructional strategy on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State. The Control Group, had a post-test mean score of 10.88 and a standard deviation of 1.590. Their retention test mean score increased slightly to 11.08, with a standard deviation of 1.498, resulting in a gain score of 0.2. This suggests that while students retained some of the knowledge gained from the post-test, the improvement was insignificant. The small gain score indicates that the traditional teaching method used for this group did not significantly enhance long-term retention of Physics concepts. For the Experimental Group (YouTube), the post-test mean score was 17.46, with a standard deviation of 1.985. Their retention test mean score increased slightly to 17.65, with a standard deviation of 3.393, resulting in a gain score of 0.2. Although the increase in retention was smaller compared to the post-test, the students in this group still retained a higher level of knowledge than those in the control group. The findings suggest that while YouTube-based instruction significantly improved students' performance in Physics, its impact on long-term retention was only slightly higher than that of the traditional method. However, the higher mean scores in both post-test

and retention test for the experimental group indicate that students exposed to YouTube instruction retained more knowledge overall.

Test on Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: There is no significant effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA analysis on effect of YouTube instructional strategies on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Posttest Score						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	553.077 ^a	2	276.539	83.959	.000	.778
Intercept	493.144	1	493.144	149.722	.000	.757
Pretest	1.002	1	1.002	.304	.584	.006
Group (Control and YouTube)	553.069	1	553.069	167.915	.000	.778
Error	158.099	48	3.294			
Total	11046.000	51				
Corrected Total	711.176	50				

a. R Squared = .778 (Adjusted R Squared = .768)

Table 3 presented the summary of ANCOVA analysis on effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State. The result revealed that YouTube instructional strategy had a significant effect on academic performance in Physics among the students ($F(1, 48) = 167.92, p < 0.05$). This means that students taught using YouTube outperformed the control group, with pretest scores having no significant influence ($p = 0.58$). The null hypothesis was rejected, indicating there is a significant effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State. Additionally, the Partial Eta squared (η^2) value of 0.778 indicates that 77.8% of the students did better than others because they were taught using Youtube. This confirms that YouTube was highly effective on understanding and academic achievement in Physics among secondary school students compared to traditional teaching methods.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant effect of YouTube instructional strategy on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA analysis on effect of YouTube instructional strategies on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects						
Dependent Variable: Youtube Retention Score						
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	591.408 ^a	2	295.704	47.140	.000	.663
Intercept	40.517	1	40.517	6.459	.014	.119
Posttest YouTube	40.623	1	40.623	6.476	.014	.119
Group (Control and YouTube)	30.083	1	30.083	4.796	.033	.091
Error	301.102	48	6.273			
Total	11514.000	51				
Corrected Total	892.510	50				

a. R Squared = .663 (Adjusted R Squared = .649)

Table 4 showed the summary of ANCOVA analysis on effect of YouTube instructional strategies on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State. The analysis shows that the overall model is statistically significant ($F(2, 48) = 47.140, p < .05$), and explains 66.3% of the variance in retention scores (Partial Eta Squared = .663). This indicates that the variables included in the model together account for a large portion of the differences in retention. The intercept was significant ($F(1, 48) = 6.459, p = .014$) though this primarily represents the baseline score. The group variable, which compares students taught using YouTube instructional strategies to those in the control group, was statistically significant ($F(1, 48) = 4.796, p = .033$) This demonstrates that the YouTube instructional strategy had a meaningful positive effect on students' retention of Physics content. Additionally, the Partial Eta squared (Eta²) value of 0.09 indicates that the effect of YouTube instructional strategy is meaningful (9.1% of variance) but smaller than its impact on initial learning. This confirms that YouTube strongly boosts immediate understanding and academic achievement in Physics among secondary school students compared to traditional teaching methods in a modest level.

DISCUSSION

Effect of YouTube instructional strategy on academic performance in Physics

The findings of this study indicated that the use of YouTube instructional tools had a large effect on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State. The results presented in Table 1 demonstrate that students exposed to YouTube-based instruction outperformed those who received traditional classroom instruction, as reflected in their post-test scores. The significant improvement in the experimental group's academic performance highlights the effectiveness of YouTube as an instructional tool for Physics education. This finding is further reinforced by the results in Table 1, which confirm a statistically significant effect of YouTube instructional tools on students' academic performance in Physics.

The findings align with the assertions of Umoh (2024), who emphasised that YouTube is one of the emerging digital tools that can be effectively incorporated into modern teaching strategies to enhance learning outcomes. Similarly, the work of Buzzetto-More, as cited by Rigdel et al. (2023), acknowledges YouTube as a vast digital library of educational content that can complement traditional teaching methods by providing interactive and engaging learning materials.

The findings of this study are consistent with previous research that highlights the benefits of YouTube as an instructional tool. Jones and Cutherll, as cited by Binni and Saidu (2021), support the use of YouTube-based training as an effective teaching tool both within and beyond the classroom. The versatility of YouTube in providing instructional videos allows students to access learning materials at their convenience, reinforcing classroom instruction and enabling self-paced learning. Jarrett, as cited by Binni and Saidu (2021), also emphasized the advantages of YouTube-based instruction, particularly its ability to enhance student-teacher interaction, student-to-student collaboration, and student-content engagement. These aspects contribute to a more interactive and participatory learning experience, ultimately leading to improved academic performance. Koustropoulos (2019) further corroborates these findings by demonstrating that the integration of YouTube videos into classroom instruction enhances student motivation, engagement, and comprehension of subject matter. The visual and auditory nature of YouTube content provides an alternative learning approach that caters to different learning styles, making complex Physics concepts more accessible and easier to understand.

Additionally, the findings align with those of Ntibi and Ibok (2020), who found that the use of YouTube in Physics instruction positively influenced students' academic performance and attitudes toward learning. The ability of YouTube to present concepts through animations, simulations, and expert demonstrations makes it an invaluable resource for improving learning outcomes. Ndiokubwayo et al. (2020) also discovered that YouTube videos significantly enhanced students' understanding of difficult Physics concepts, leading to better academic performance. The visual representation of abstract concepts, such as projectile motion, linear momentum, and acceleration, provides students with a clearer understanding of the subject matter. This is supported by Jill et al. (2019), who found that incorporating YouTube videos

into Physics lessons increased students' interest and engagement, thereby improving their overall academic performance.

Effect of YouTube instructional strategy on retention in Physics

The findings from Table 2 revealed that the YouTube instructional tool has a long-term effect on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State. This suggests that students who were taught using YouTube instructional videos retained the knowledge they gained over time. However, Table 2 presents supported this, showing that there is a significant effect of YouTube instructional strategies on retention in Physics among the students. Several studies support the assertion that YouTube instructional tools positively impact students' learning experiences, particularly in subjects that require visualization and conceptual understanding. Jackman (2019) argued that YouTube is among the innovative e-learning resources that can be effectively integrated into education. The platform offers diverse instructional videos that help reinforce learning through multimedia engagement. According to Buzzetto-More, as referenced by Rigdel et al. (2023), YouTube serves as a vast repository of educational content that can supplement traditional teaching methods, making complex topics more accessible to students. Similarly, Jones and Cutherll, as cited in Binni and Saidu (2021), highlight that YouTube-based instruction facilitates learning both inside and outside the classroom, providing students with flexibility and additional resources for independent study.

Furthermore, Jarrett, as referenced in Binni and Saidu (2021), highlights that YouTube's educational benefits extend beyond content delivery. It fosters interaction between students and teachers, as well as peer-to-peer engagement, enhancing knowledge retention through collaborative learning. Research by Koustropoulos (2019) indicates that integrating YouTube videos in lessons increases students' motivation, engagement, and comprehension. This aligns with findings from Ndiokubwayo et al. (2020), who discovered that YouTube significantly improved students' academic performance and understanding of difficult Physics concepts by presenting information in a visually engaging manner. Additionally, You and Kang (2020) observed that the inclusion of YouTube videos in Physics lessons increased students' interest and participation, reinforcing their ability to retain information more effectively.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that YouTube instructional strategy enhances academic performance and retention in physics among secondary school student in Rivers State. There should be incorporation of YouTube-based learning resources into the Physics curriculum to boost students' academic performance since it had a significant effect on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Educational policymakers should incorporate YouTube-based learning resources into the Physics curriculum to boost students' academic performance since it had a significant effect on academic performance in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. Since there was a significant effect of YouTube instructional strategy on retention in Physics among secondary school students in Rivers State. Teachers should combine YouTube videos with other interactive learning strategies, such as quizzes and discussions, to improve students' retention in Physics.

REFERENCES

- Abubakar, Z. (2024). Effect of virtual learning strategy on biology students' achievement in Gwagwalada Area Council, FCT-Abuja. *American Journal of Integrated STEM Education*, 1(2), 1–10.
- Ayoola, Y. A. (2023). Assessment of students' retention level on learning of Physics in senior secondary schools using inquiry-based and computer-assisted instruction methods. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Education*, 7(1), 275-283.

- Babagana, M., Yaki, A. A., & Abubakar, Z. (2021). Impact of field trip and demonstration instructional strategies on senior secondary school students' achievement and retention on the concept of pollution in biology, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 4(12), 1-9.
- Falode, O. C., Sobowale, M. F., Saliu, R. M., Usman, H., & Falode, M. E. (2016). Effectiveness of computer animation instructional package on academic achievement of senior secondary school agricultural science students in animal physiology in Minna, Nigeria. *Bulgarian Journal of Science and Education Policy*, 10(1), 5-14.
- Garrett-Wright, D. M., & Abell, C. H. (2017). Using YouTube to bridge the gap between baby boomers and millennials. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 50(5), 299-300.
- Kumar, S., Agarwal, M., & Agarwal, N. (2021). Defining and measuring academic performance of HEI students: A critical review. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 12(6), 3091-3105.
- Lima, C. D., Bastos, R. C., & Varvakis, G. (2020). Digital learning platforms: an integrative review to support internationalization of higher education. *Education in Review*, 36, e232826.
- Mohammed, I. A., & Ogar, S. I. (2023). Exploring the potential of YouTube videos towards enhancing achievement and retention of undergraduate students in environmental education. *European Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Education*, 4(1), e02302. <https://doi.org/10.30935/ejimed/13190>
- Narad, A., & Abdullah, B. (2016). Academic performance of senior secondary school students: Influence of parental encouragement and school environment. *Rupkatha Journal on Interdisciplinary Studies in Humanities*, 3(2), 12-19.
- Ndihokubwayo, K., Uwamahoro, J., & Ndayambaje, I. (2020). Effectiveness of PhET simulations and YouTube videos to improve the learning of optics in Rwandan secondary schools. *African Journal of Research in Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 24(2), 253-265.
- Ntibi, J. E. E., & Ibok, E. E. (2020). Students' WhatsApp and YouTube usage as determinants of academic achievement in Physics in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Journal of the Social Sciences*, 48(3).
- Nwile, C. B., & Onojakaromah, G. (2022). Perceived Influence of School Principals' Leadership Style on Students' Academic Performance in Senior Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation* 8(2), 11-25.
- Ogunode, N. J., Johnson, A. G., & Olatunde-Aiyedun, T. G. (2022). Education crisis in Nigeria and way forward. In *Kresna Social Science and Humanities Research Proceedings of the International Conference on Sustainable Development: Problems, Analysis and Prospects* (pp. 33-47).
- Songkram, N., & Osuwan, H. (2022). Applying the technology acceptance model to elucidate K-12 teachers' use of digital learning platforms in Thailand during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Sustainability*, 14(10), 6027. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14106027>
- Umoh, E. (2024). YouTube as an Effective Digital Tool for Learning in Emerging Economy: Opportunities and Challenges. *YouTube as an Effective Digital Tool for Learning in Emerging Economy: Opportunities and Challenges* (May 05, 2024).
- Zalmon, I. G., & Arokoyu, A. (2021). Effect of Polya's Problem Solving Strategy on Senior Secondary School Students. *Nigerian Journal of Curriculum Theorists And Educational Technologists* Vol, 6(1), 115-129.